

ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ ПРОЕКТНОГО ОБУЧЕНИЯ В ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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RESEARCH ON THE EFFECTIVENESS OF PROJECT-BASED LEARNING TECHNOLOGY IN GEOGRAPHIC EDUCATION

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В настоящее время развитие у учащихся исследовательских способностей, приобщение к самообразованию является одной из важнейших проблем в системе образования. Одним из возможных путей решения данной проблемы является применение технологии проектного обучения. Технология проектного обучения развивает у учащихся способность решать проблемы, повышая мотивацию к получению пособия. Но в нашей стране технология проектного обучения в географическом образовании не получила широкого распространения.

Целью данной работы является экспериментальная оценка эффективности технологии проектного обучения в преподавании школьной географии.

Эксперимент состоял из 2 частей:

1) онлайн опрос;

2) эксперимент с участием 36 учеников десятого класса, где учащиеся были разделены на 2 группы: экспериментальную и контрольную;

Эксперимент длился 9 недель и состоял из 7 уроков и 2 экзаменов. В то время как экспериментальная группа получала образование с помощью технологии проектного обучения, контрольная группа имела простые занятия. Занятия проводились по разделу «природопользование и геоэкология». Итоговые результаты показали, что в среднем учащиеся групповой экспериментальной группы более активно посещали занятия и набрали в среднем на 3,07 балла выше в тесте, чем в контрольной группе. Разница в баллах между этими двумя группами показала, что технология проектного обучения является эффективным инструментом обучения и может быть использована в общеобразовательных школах для углубления географических знаний учащихся и повышения их исследовательских способностей.

ABSTRACT

Currently, the development of students' research abilities and the introduction to self-education is one of the most important problems in the education system. One of the possible ways to solve this problem is the use of project-based learning technology. Project-based learning technology develops students' ability to solve problems, increasing motivation to receive benefits. But in our country, the technology of project-based learning in geography education has not been widely used.

The purpose of this work is an experimental assessment of the effectiveness of project-based learning technology in teaching school geography.

The experiment consisted of 2 parts:

1) Online survey;

2) an experiment involving 36 tenth grade students, where the students were divided into 2 groups: experimental and control;

The experiment lasted 9 weeks and consisted of 7 lessons and 2 exams. While the experimental group was educated using project-based learning technology, the control group had simple classes. Classes were held in the section "environmental management and geoecology". The final results showed that, on average, the students of the experimental group attended classes more actively and scored an average of 3.07 points higher in the test than in the control group. The difference in scores between these two groups showed that project-based learning technology is an effective teaching tool and can be used in general education schools to deepen students' geographical knowledge and enhance their research abilities.

Ключевые слова: проект, технология проектного обучения (PBL), школьная география, географическое образование, преимущества технологии проектного обучения.

Keywords: project, project learning technology (PBL), school geography, geographical education, advantages of project learning technology.

Introduction. Nowadays, education is aimed at educating an individual who can solve problems, adapt knowledge to real life, and engage in lifelong learning [1]. In order to form such a personality in education, teachers use many educational technologies [2,3,4]. One of them is project-based learning technology.

Project-based learning refers to a query-based learning method that engages students in building knowledge that motivates them to perform meaningful projects and develop real-world products.[5]

Project-based learning allows students to learn by following and applying ideas. Students engage in real-world activities that resemble the activities that adult professionals engage in[6]. This technology makes the learning process more active and does not let students get bored. In this way, it improves students' learning outcomes, increases their scientific research skills, and has a significant impact on students' problem-solving abilities[7].

The project-based teaching methodology is more popular than ever and is used in a wide range of education and training in the world [8]. And project - based teaching of geography encourages a dynamic educational approach that combines real-world problem solving and critical thinking[9]. Many sources support the effectiveness of this method. Confirms its influence on the activity of students and a deeper understanding of geographical concepts[10,11].

In their work, Shen and Yang compared the impact of students on academic achievement in primary, secondary and higher education through project-based learning technology on the direct instruction of teachers. Project-based learning in this study reflects the learning process in which students are engaged in original projects and the development of products. As a result, project-based learning had a more positive impact on students' academic achievement than direct learning[12].

R. D. Putri proved in his research that project-based learning technology has a beneficial effect on the spatial thinking of students. Geography is a science that focuses on the knowledge and study of space. However, it has been proven that the spatial thinking of students shows significantly more positive results when learning with project-based learning technology than cognitive work carried out in the field [13].

Indonesian scientists D. Arisanti et al. used project-based learning technology in order to effectively teach geography at Banjarmasin high school. The study was conducted on 2 groups of 11 classes. As a result, the use of project-based learning technology in teaching geography has proven that it not only affects the improvement of the quality of education, but also affects the activity of students. In the course of the study, students have increased creative abilities and developed research skills [11].

Looking at these studies, we can see that project-based learning technology develops students' knowledge and skills. Therefore, in order to improve the effectiveness of geographical education, it is necessary to use project-based learning technologies.

The purpose of this study is aimed at assessing the effectiveness of project-based learning technology in teaching geography.

Research methods. The study was designed as a multi-method study using a quasi-experimental design and a descriptive quantitative research method with a control group of students in the 10th grade before and after the test.

Two groups (experimental and control) with the same levels take part in the study. The levels of the groups are determined by the test. The experimental group is trained with project-based learning technology, the control group is trained with a traditional format for 7 weeks. After the end of the practical classes, a post-Practical Test was conducted again. A study was carried out using the T-test method in order to compare the similarities and differences between the results of the two groups. The average value of the two groups, the standard deviation, the degree of freedom of testing, and the level of significance of the results were also calculated. To calculate the mean and standard deviation (SD) values "Calculator.net" online calculation program, and for the calculation of the T-test and the analysis of quantitative data "Graphpad.com" online software was used.

Participants. The study involved 36 students of the tenth grade of school-Lyceum No. 210 in Almaty. The number of students in the experimental group was 15, and the number of students in the control group was 21. The study participants were not classified by any method. Class 10 A was randomly selected as the experimental group and Class 10 B as the control group. 8 of the students in the experimental group were boys, 7 were girls. 14 of them are educational accents, 1 is secondary. 10 students in the control group are girls, 11 are boys. 19 educational accents, 2 secondary ones. The age of the students ranged from 15-17 years.

Data collection. To collect the data, a 30-question test developed by the researchers was used. In the process of preparing and compiling the test, a table of specifications and goals of the section "nature management and geocology" in the curriculum of geography of the tenth grade was developed. To verify the validity of the test, questions about the training goals were determined according to the complexity of each goal in relation to the General section. In addition, two teachers of the Russian language and literature considered the questions from the point of view of language and meaning. Based on their feedback, the necessary adjustments were made to the test. The level of complexity of the test was also checked by 2 Geography teachers with an expert degree, and the necessary changes were made according to feedback.

Implementation. The implementation of the study took from one hour a week to 9 weeks. Before the execution, a test was applied to both groups to determine their equivalence. After using the preliminary test, the students in the control group conducted simple lessons with an interactive whiteboard, a textbook, repeated the lesson using the question-answer method and completed the tasks in the textbook as tasks. And in the experimental group, tasks compiled on the basis of project-based learning technology were used as

teaching tools. The tasks were developed using digital technologies (main map, CorelDRAW, Flippity, Padlet, Miro, etc.). To compile the tasks, a textbook of the tenth grade for teaching geography of the natural and mathematical direction, compiled by K. Kaimuldinova, S. Abilmazhinova, was used. In the process of compiling the tasks, special attention was paid to the purpose of the geography course of the tenth grade, the age characteristics of the students and the correspondence of the task to their level.

Based on feedback from three geography teachers, two class teachers, 79 students of the tenth grade of

school-Lyceum No. 210, where the pilot study was conducted, the necessary changes were made to the project tasks. During the lesson, project tasks were completed and instructions for completing the task were shown. The task of the teacher is to guide the students. All sources of information were provided by the teacher in advance and showed an example to explain the task to the students. For this reason, the instruction to the teacher about all the necessary information was given before the experiment. During the lesson, special attention was paid to the implementation of project tasks.

An example of tasks completed in the course of the study.

Suggest ways to improve the environmental situation in Kazakhstan

Figure 1-suggest ways to improve the environmental situation in Kazakhstan.

1. study of environmental problems
 - a) identify and thoroughly study the main environmental problems in Kazakhstan.
 - b) provide statistical data, case studies and examples to illustrate the severity of these difficulties.
2. analysis of the local ecosystem
 - a) carry out a detailed analysis of local ecosystems, focusing on rivers, lakes, forests and other natural resources.
 - b) assess the impact of human activity on these ecosystems and propose conservation strategies.
3. offer solutions for renewable energy
 - a) Explore and propose viable renewable energy options that meet the unique geographical and climatic conditions of Kazakhstan.

- b) discuss the potential benefits and difficulties associated with the adoption of renewable energy sources.
4. biodiversity conservation strategies
 - a) explore measures to protect and preserve biodiversity in Kazakhstan.
 - b) emphasize the importance of preserving endangered species and ecosystems.
5. development of green infrastructure
 - a) Explore and propose ways to incorporate green infrastructure into urban development.
 - b) propose sustainable urban planning strategies to minimize the impact on the environment.
6. improving waste management
 - a) evaluate current waste management practices in Kazakhstan and identify areas for improvement.

- b) offer innovative waste reduction and recycling programs.
- 7. policy recommendations
 - a) study of environmental policy in Kazakhstan.
 - b) propose additional policy proposals or amendments to improve the protection and sustainability of the environment.

Results. This histogram contains the results of tests performed before and after the practice session. The time interval between pre-and post-test tests is 7 weeks. All data are analyzed by Student's T-test and the degrees of validity of the test are presented.

Figure 2-pre-experimental results of 15 students in the experimental group.

Figure 3-results of pre-practical testing of 21 students in the control group.

Figures 1 and 2 show the results obtained in advance by the experimental group and the control group. You can see the number of pupils in the horizontal direction, and the results in the vertical direction.

Table 1

Unpaired preliminary test results of 2 groups of students with T-test and p-values						
Groups	students	average value	SD	df	t test	p value
Experimental	15	23,93	2.38	34	0.1784	0.8595
Control group	21	23,76	2.95			

The first table presents the pre-experimental score values of the two groups, the SD (Standard Deviation) standard deviation values and the T-test and p-values. The results of the two groups are similar to each other, as shown in the table. The average score for the experimental group was 23.93, and for the experimental group-23.76. the standard deviations were 2.95 in the

control group, and 2.38 in the experimental group. the T-test stool value was 0.1784. The p value was a coefficient of 0.8595. These indicators show that there is no significant statistical difference between the two groups, that is, the level of knowledge of students in the groups is the same.

Figure 4-post-experimental results of 15 students in the experimental group.

Figure 5-post-practice results of 21 students in the control group.

Figures 3 and 4 show the results of the observation group and the experimental group after the experiment. You can see the number of pupils in the horizontal direction, and the results in the vertical direction.

Table 2

Results of unpaired post-experimental tests of students of two groups with T-test and p-values						
Groups	students	average value	SD	df	t test	p value
Experimental	15	27.07	2.15	34	3.5913	0.0010
Control group	21	24.00	2.76			

Table 2 shows the SD, T-test and P values of the experimental group and control group. Statistical analysis of the results of post-practice testing of students shows that there is a difference between the two groups. In the observational group, the average value showed 24, in the experimental group this figure is higher by a coefficient of 3.07. The SD score was 2.76 in the control group and 2.15 in the experimental group. The degree of freedom of the general test is equal to 34. The value of T was 3.5913, the value of P was equal to the indicator 0.0010. According to the results of the T-test of both groups, the diversity of groups can be expressed with 95% confidence.

At the same time, after the use of project-based learning technology in teaching geography, a number of positive changes were observed not only in the indicators of students' knowledge, but also in their critical thinking, collaboration with classmates, differentiation of Information, development of research abilities, and interconnection of subjects.

During the practice, Project-Based Learning revealed different points of view, alternative solutions, and contradictions to students. This helped students develop critical thinking and analysis skills.

Students who mastered project-based learning were able not only to learn geographical facts, but also to connect processes with each other and form a deeper geographical understanding.

In the process of joint consideration of geographical issues, they also learned to use each other's strengths. And this strengthens the ability of students to work harmoniously with the team and prepares them for the future.

Conclusion and discussion. In conclusion, it was proved on the basis of experience that the use of project-based learning technology in geographical education helps to improve the quality of students' knowledge. Initially, the level of knowledge of the two groups of students selected for the purpose of practice was approximately equal. That is, they have similar average indicators of pre-trial testing results. Then, for 7 weeks, two groups of 10th grade students received training in the Department "Nature management and geocology" in two different formats (experimental group-with Project-Based Learning Technology, Control Group-in the traditional educational format).

According to the results of post-experimental testing, the average score of the experimental group was higher than that of the control group by a coefficient of 3.07. Initially, the T-criterion showed that there is no point in statistical comparison of these results. And after using project-based learning technology, this result was negative. After the experiment, it was found that the t value is 3.5913 p value is 0.0010. That is, the statistical results of the groups are 95% different.

In this article, we dealt with the assessment of the effectiveness of project-based learning technology in teaching geography. First of all, we studied the effectiveness of project-based learning technology. For this purpose, we conducted practical training in 210 schools-lyceums of Almaty.

Based on the research of foreign scientists, project-based learning has a moderate to large positive effect on students' learning outcomes compared to traditional learning [12,14,15]. Analyzing the work of foreign experience and scientists, it was revealed that the use of project-based learning technologies in basic education is of great importance. Therefore, we thought that project-based learning would be more effective than traditional learning. Based on the results after the experiment, the students of the experimental group achieved a good result of the study. That is, we were able to prove that project-based learning technology is an effective discipline in teaching geography.

In addition, project learning technology promotes critical thinking, problem solving, interpersonal communication, information and media literacy, collaboration, leadership and teamwork, innovation and creative thinking [16,17,18,19]. This conclusion of scientists corresponded to our personal experience. The students showed these qualities and became more active in the lesson.

Many studies show that project learning technology is one of the most effective ways to develop opportunities in the 21st century [20,21]. We also propose to use project-based learning technologies in order to increase the effectiveness of teaching geography at school, based on the results of the practice conducted in 210 schools-lyceums.

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